

Polarographic Study of Zn(II)—Thiocyanate System

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Polarographic behaviour of Zn(II) in the presence of increasing [thiocyanate] has been studied at a constant ionic strength $\mu=2$ (NaNO_3). The reduction has been found to be diffusion controlled and quasi-reversible $E_{1/2}$ of Zn(II) gets shifted to more negative potentials with increasing [thiocyanate] thereby showing complex formation. The reversible half-wave potential, ($E_{1/2}^r$) and the kinetic parameters of the electrode process have been evaluated by Gellings method. Zn(II) forms three successive complexes: $[\text{Zn}(\text{CNS})]^+$, $[\text{Zn}(\text{CNS})_2]$ and $[\text{Zn}(\text{CNS})_3]^-$ and not four as reported by earlier workers¹. Stability constants of the three complexes are $\beta_1=3$, $\beta_2=4$ and $\beta_3=10$. The percentage distribution of Zn(II) in its various forms as a function of ligand concentration has also been presented.

FRANK and Hume¹ have studied polarographically the Zn(II)-thiocyanate system at a constant ionic strength $\mu=2$ and have reported the formation of four successive complex species with stability constant $\beta_1=3\pm 0.5$, $\beta_2=7\pm 3$, $\beta_3=1\pm 1$ and $\beta_4=20\pm 2$. A perusal of these values, however, shows that the formation of third successive complex species viz., $[\text{Zn}(\text{CNS})_3]^{1-}$ with $\beta_3=1\pm 1$ is doubtful as a value of $\beta=1$ signifies the stability constant of the "zero complex"². It seems, prima facie, that Zn(II) forms only three successive complexes. It was therefore thought worthwhile to verify the results of Frank and Hume. Apart from this, the nature of electrode reaction of Zn(II) in the presence of increasing thiocyanate concentration has also been ascertained and the kinetic parameters of the electrode reaction have been determined.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of AR, BDH or E. Merck G. R. grade and their solutions were prepared in conductivity water by standard analytical procedures. NaNO_3 solution was used to keep the ionic strength constant ($\mu=2$). KCNS solution was used as ligand. The concentration of Zn(II) in each case was kept $1 \times 10^{-3}M$.

A manual polarograph in conjunction with Toshniwal Polyflex galvanometer (PL-50) was used. All the measurements were made at $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$. Purified nitrogen gas was passed through the solution to deaerate it. Saturated Calomel Electrode (S. C. E.) was used as a reference electrode. The d.m.e. had the following characteristics (in $0.1M$ NaNO_3 , open circuit). $m=2.459$ mg/sec; $t=2.44$ sec; $m^{2/3}t^{1/3}=2.11$ $\text{mg}^{2/3} \text{sec}^{-1/3}$; $h_{\text{corr}}=61.79$ cm.

The number of electrons (n) involved in the reduction process was determined by millicoulometric method by DeVries and Kroon³ using a mercury pool cathode. This gave the value of $n=2$.

Results and Discussion

A series of polarograms were obtained with different concentrations of ligand. The thiocyanate concentration was varied from 0 to $2M$. In each case a single well defined diffusion controlled wave appeared. The plots of i_d vs $\sqrt{h_{\text{corr}}}$ were found to be linear passing through origin indicating that the reduction is diffusion controlled. The plots of $\log i/i_d - i$ vs $E_{\text{d.e.}}$ were found to be linear with slope of the order of 40 ± 2 mV showing the quasi-reversible nature of electrode reaction^{4,5}.

The reversible half-wave potential has been calculated by Gellings⁶ method. DeFord and Humes⁷ method modified by Irving⁸ has been

Fig. 1. Percentage distribution of Zn(II) in its various forms as a function of [thiocyanate]

○ → Zn²⁺
● → [Zn(CNS)]⁺
▲ → [Zn(CNS)₂]
△ → [Zn(CNS)₃]⁻

applied to determine the composition and stability constants of the successive complexes (Table 2).

TABLE 1—POLAROGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS OF Zn(II)-THIOCYANATE SYSTEM, $\mu=2$

[Thiocyanate] M	$-\frac{E_{1/2}}{V}$ (S.C.E.)	$-\frac{E_{1/2}^r}{V}$ (S.C.E.)	α	$k_{sh} \times 10^3$ cm/sec
0	0.985	0.970	0.997	1.08
0.1	0.990	0.975	0.704	1.414
0.2	0.995	0.975	0.645	1.318
0.4	1.000	0.986	0.645	1.745
0.6	1.010	0.995	0.607	1.383
0.8	1.030	1.010	0.704	1.658
2.0	1.050	1.030	0.645	0.707

TABLE 2—VALUES OF $F_1[X]$ FUNCTIONS AT DIFFERENT CONCENTRATIONS OF THIOCYANATE

[Thiocyanate] M	$F_0[X]$	$F_1[X]$	$F_2[X]$	$F_3[X]$
0	—	—	—	—
0.1	1.420	4.20	—	—
0.2	1.521	2.60	—	—
0.4	3.442	6.03	7.575	8.937
0.6	7.086	10.143	11.905	13.175
0.8	10.420	11.775	10.968	—
1.0	20.700	19.700	16.700	12.700
2.0	103.300	51.150	24.070	10.035

$\beta_1=3$; $\beta_2=4$; $\beta_3=10$.

The stability constants for three complexes: $[Zn(CNS)]^+$, $[Zn(CNS)_2]$ and $[Zn(CNS)_3]^-$ are $\beta_1=3$, $\beta_2=4$ and $\beta_3=10$. Fig. 1 represents the percentage distribution of Zn(II) in its various forms as a function of $[CNS^-]$.

The kinetic parameters (α and k_{sh}) of electrode reaction of Zn(II)-thiocyanate system has been calculated by Gellings method and are listed in Table 1. The value of k_{sh} is of the order of 2×10^{-3} cm/sec showing⁹⁻¹¹ the quasi-reversible nature of the electrode process.

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